

Review on novel approach to enhancement MRI image Brain tumor detection using SVM and Artificial neural network algorithm.

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Abstract- Brain tumor segmentation is an important task in medical image processing. Early diagnosis of brain tumors plays an important role in improving treatment possibilities and increases the survival rate of the patients. Manual segmentation of the brain tumors for cancer diagnosis, from large amount of MRI images generated in clinical routine, is a difficult and time consuming task. There is a need for automatic brain tumor image segmentation. The purpose of this paper is to provide a review of MRI-based brain tumor segmentation methods. Recently, automatic segmentation using deep learning methods proved popular since these methods achieve the state-of-the-art results and can address this problem better than other methods. Deep learning methods can also enable efficient processing and objective evaluation of the large amounts of MRI-based image data. There are number of existing review papers, focusing on traditional methods for MRI-based brain tumor image segmentation. Different than others, in this paper, we focus on the recent trend of deep learning methods in this field. First, an introduction to brain tumors and methods for brain tumor segmentation is given. Then, the state-of-the-art algorithms with a focus on recent trend of deep learning methods are discussed. Finally, an assessment of the current state is presented and future developments to standardize MRI-based brain tumor segmentation methods into daily clinical routine are addressed.

Index Terms- Review; image processing; deep learning; brain tumor segmentation; convolutional neural networks; MRI.

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical image processing is the most vast and important field today. This project describes the methodology of detection & extraction of brain tumor from patient's MRI scan images of the brain. In this project, a method for segmentation of brain tumor has been developed on MRI data which allows the identification of Tumor tissue with high accuracy and reproductability compared to manual techniques. This method incorporates with some noise removal functions and segmentation which are the basic concepts of Image processing [1]. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is an enhanced medical imaging technique used to produce high quality images. From these high-resolution images, we can easily extract the detailed information to examine human brain development and discover abnormalities. The MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) has become more useful medical diagnostic tool for diagnosis of brain and other medical images. The process to detect the brain tumors through MRI images can be categorized into four different sections; pre-processing, image segmentation, feature extraction and image classification [2]. The Brain Tumor is affecting many people worldwide. Brain Tumor is the abnormal growth of cell inside the brain which limits the functioning of the brain. It can effect proper brain function and be life-threatening also. Two types of brain tumors have been identified as Malignant and Benign.

Malignant tumors are fast growing and cancerous. Benign are slow growing and non-cancerous and less harmful than malignant. Early detection of the brain tumor is possible with the advancement of Image Processing (IP) [3]. The Pre-Processing, Segmentation, Optimization and Feature Extraction followed by classification, size and volume detection and stage detection. These techniques allow us to identify even the smallest abnormalities in the human brain. The goal of medical imaging is to extract accurate information from these images with the least error possible; it converts the original image to a compact form.

II. RESEARCH MOTIVATION

Uncontrolled cell growth and division may be described as cancer. These abnormal cell growth and divisions in the brain tissue are known as brain tumours when they occur in large numbers. Despite their rarity, brain tumours are one of the deadliest forms of cancer [1]. The aberrant proliferation of brain cells in an uncontrolled fashion is known as a brain tumour [2, 3]. Cancerous and non-cancerous brain tumours are also possible. The gravitational pull of the skull may accelerate a brain tumor's development. A severe brain injury may be life-threatening in the worst-case scenario. More than 18,000 people will die in 2020 from primary brain and central nervous system cancers. Brain tumours are present in various ways on

magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans. [4, 5]. MRI scans are thus common to identify and categorise brain cancers. For physicians, an MRI is an invaluable tool for determining the best course of therapy for malignancies. Many variables influence this therapy, including cancer's shape, grade, size, and location. These characteristics might vary greatly depending on the patient's health. It is why it is so important for the appropriate diagnosis and categorisation of brain tumours to be accurate. [6]

Pre-Processing Methods

The reasons for the image degradation are the following reasons: the image's resolution will be low, artifacts present, improper contrast, and high-frequency noise or speckle noises. These imperfections can be reduced by employing pre-processing methods such as image re-sampling, gray scale contrast enhancement, Morphological operations (Dilation, erosion, opening, and closing), and histogram equalisation [3].

III. SEGMENTATION

Segmentation subdivides an image into its constituent regions or objects and it should stop when the objects or regions of interest in an application have been detected. Segmentation is process of partitioning the image into different parts having similar features. The pre-processing stages needs to done on the image initially, and then segmentation and feature extraction is applied for the detection of the tumor which is the region of interest (ROI) from the entire image. The features are intensity based, area base, is the vital part of segmentation as the tumor must be isolated from the brain image. For brain image segmentation numerous image processing techniques have been proposed, for example- region growing, thresholding, classifiers and clustering.

Feature Extraction

Features, the characteristics of the objects of interest, if selected carefully are representative of the maximum relevant information that the image has to offer for a complete characterization of a lesion. Feature extraction methodologies analyze objects and images to extract the most prominent features that are representative of the various classes of objects. Features are used as inputs to classifiers that assign them to the class that they represent. The purpose of feature extraction is to reduce the original data by measuring certain properties, or features, that distinguish one input pattern from another pattern. The extracted feature should provide the characteristics of the input type to the classifier by considering the description of the relevant properties of the image into feature vectors. In this proposed method we extract the following features.

- Shape Features - circularity, irregularity, Area, Perimeter, Shape Index
- Intensity features – Mean, Variance, Standard Variance, Median Intensity, Skewness, and Kurtosis.
- Texture features – Contrast, Correlation, Entropy, Energy, Homogeneity, cluster shade, sum of square variance.

IV. CLASSIFICATION

The SVM is a supervised learning method. It is a good tool for data analysis and classification. SVM classifier has a fast learning speed even in large data. SVM is used for two or more class classification problems. Support Vector Machine is based on the conception of decision planes. A decision plane is one that separates between a set of items having dissimilar class memberships. The Classification and detection of brain tumor was done by using the Support Vector Machine technique. Classification is done to identify the tumor class present in the image. The use of SVM involves two basic steps of training and testing.

V. PERFORMANCE MEASURING METRICS

Evaluating the segmentation and classification performance of a machine learning algorithm is an essential part of a research project. A machine learning model may give a satisfying result when evaluated using a metric, for instance, accuracy score but may give poor results when evaluated against other metrics such as precision or any other metric. Therefore, most of the time various evaluation metrics are applied to measure and compare the model performance.

In a segmentation task, true positive (TP) represents a pixel that is correctly predicted to belong to the given class according to the ground truth, whereas a true negative (TN) represents a pixel that is correctly identified as not belonging to the given class. On the other hand, a false positive (FP) is an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts a pixel not belonging to a given class. A false negative (FN) is an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts the pixel belonging to a given class. Similarly, for tumor classification task, TP represents a tumor class that is correctly predicted to belong to the given class according to the ground truth whereas a TN represents a tumor class that is correctly identified as not belonging to the given class. By the same token, false positive (FP) is an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts a tumor class not belonging to a given class. A false negative (FN) is an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts the class belonging to a given class.

VI. ANALYSIS OF PROBLEM

Now days, one of the main cause for increasing mortality among children and adults is brain tumor. It has been concluded from the research of most of the developed countries that number of people suffering and dying from brain tumors has been increased to 300 per year during past few decades. The National Brain Tumor Foundation (NBTF) for research in United States estimates the death of 13000 patients while 29,000 undergo primary brain tumor diagnosis. This high mortality rate of brain tumor greatly increases the importance of Brain Tumor detection. Real time diagnosis of tumors by

using more reliable algorithms has been the main focus of the latest developments in medical imaging and detection of brain tumor in MR Mages and CT scan images has been an active research area. The separation of the cells and their nuclei from the rest of the image content is one of the main problems faced by most of the medical imagery diagnosis systems. The process of separation i.e. segmentation, is paid at most importance in the construction of a robust diagnosis system. Image segmentation is performed on the input images. This enables easier analysis of the image thereby leading to better tumor detection efficiency. Hence image segmentation is the fundamental problem in tumor detection.

VII. LITERATURE REVIEW

Venkata Subba Reddy Gade et al. [1] Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain is the gold standard for diagnosing degenerative neurological conditions such as brain tumours, strokes, dementia, and Multiple sclerosis (MS). For the purpose of health monitoring, MRI scans, a plethora of deep learning-based medical image processing approaches have been presented. After a fully linked network, a convolution neural network (CNN) is the next best structure. While it excels at improving local features and is translation invariant, it has trouble getting global features. In order to make up for CNNs' flaws and efficiently get global characteristics, transformers can be used. Unfortunately, the calculated number of transformers is too high. An improved Lite Swin transformer (OLiST) is offered as a viable solution to this issue. Our proposed OLiST model takes advantage of both the global feature acquisition capability of the Lite Swin transformer and the capability of the CNN by combining the features extracted by the two and then sampling them up gradually. The barnacles mating optimizer (BMO) for hyper-parameter optimization in the LiST model enhances its performance in detecting brain tumours. Kaggle database photos of open-source brain tumours re used. Testing the suggested deep learning perfectly with other ll-known transfer learning approaches on the same MRI dataset resulted in an increase in processing time and improved classification results.

Erdal Özbay et al. [2] Brain tumor is a deadly disease that can affect people of all ages. Radiologists play a critical role in the early diagnosis and treatment of the 14,000 persons diagnosed with brain tumors on average each year. The best method for tumor detection with computer-aided diagnosis systems (CADs) is Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). However, manual evaluation using conventional approaches may result in a number of inaccuracies due to the complicated tissue properties of a large number of images. Therefore a precision medical image hashing approach is proposed that combines interpretability and feature fusion using MRI images of brain tumors, to address the issue of medical image retrieval.

Almetwally Mohamad Mostafa et al. [3] Irregular growth of cells in the skull is recognized as a brain tumor that can have two types such as benign and malignant. There exist various methods which are used by oncologists to assess the existence of brain tumors such as blood tests or visual assessments. Moreover, the noninvasive magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) technique without ionizing radiation has been commonly utilized for diagnosis. However, the segmentation in 3-dimensional MRI is time-consuming and the outcomes mainly depend on the operator's experience. Therefore, a novel and robust automated brain tumor detector has been suggested based on segmentation and fusion of features. To improve the localization results, we pre-processed the images using Gaussian Filter (GF), and SynthStrip: a tool for brain skull stripping. We utilized two known benchmarks for training and testing i.e., Figshare and Harvard. The proposed methodology attained 99.8% accuracy, 99.3% recall, 99.4% precision, 99.5% F1 score, and 0.989 AUC. We performed the comparative analysis of our approach with prevailing DL, classical, and segmentation-based approaches. Additionally, we also performed the cross-validation using Harvard dataset attaining 99.3% identification accuracy. The outcomes exhibit that our approach offers significant outcomes than existing methods and outperforms them.

Remya Ajai et al. [4] A S Brain Tumors are the leading cause of cancer death in children. They are caused by the abnormal and uncontrolled growth of cells inside the brain or spinal canal. Classification of brain tumors using machine learning technology is very relevant for radiologists to confirm their analysis more effectively and quickly. Segmentation algorithm identified for detecting the tumor from the MRI brain scans need to detect shapeless tumor growth perfectly. Sobel edge detection is one of the widely used edge detection techniques in which only information along horizontal and vertical directions are considered. In this research, Sobel algorithm with 8-directional template is implemented for improving the detection of edges in brain tumor MRI images. The proposed algorithm is compared with other traditional edge detection algorithms. The performance of the proposed algorithm is analyzed in terms of MSE, RMSE, Entropy, SNR and PSNR. Analysis shows that 8-Sobel is comparatively the most suitable technique for analyzing brain tumor MRI images. Active contouring segmentation algorithm is applied on the edge detected images to verify the classification accuracy of segmented tumor.

Arkapravo Chattopadhyay et al. [5] In this paper, we proposed an algorithm to segment brain tumours from 2D Magnetic Resonance brain Images (MRI) by a convolutional neural network which is followed by traditional classifiers and deep learning methods. We have taken various MRI images with diverse Tumour sizes, locations, shapes, and different image intensities to train the model well. Furthermore, we have applied SVM classifier and other activation algorithms

(softmax, RMSProp, sigmoid, etc) to cross-check our work. We implement our proposed method using “TensorFlow” and “Keras” in “Python” as it is an efficient programming language to perform fast work.

M.O. Khairandish et al. [6] Deep learning (DL) methods due to good performance in the last few years have become more popular for Image classification. Convolution Neural Network (CNN), with several methods, can extract features without using handcrafted models, and eventually, show better accuracy of classification. The proposed hybrid model combined CNN and support vector machine (SVM) in terms of classification and with threshold-based segmentation in terms of detection.

Raheleh Hashemzahi et al. [7] A brain tumor is an abnormal growth of cells inside the skull. Malignant brain tumors are among the most dreadful types of cancer with direct consequences such as cognitive decline and poor quality of life. Analyzing magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a popular technique for brain tumor detection. In this paper, we use these images to train our new hybrid paradigm which consists of a neural autoregressive distribution estimation (NADE) and a convolutional neural network (CNN). We subsequently test this model with 3064 T1-weighted contrast-enhanced images with three types of brain tumors. The results demonstrate that the hybrid CNN-NADE has a high classification performance as regards the availability of medical images are limited.

D. Rammurth et al. [8] The detection of Brain cancer is an essential process, which is based on the clinician’s knowledge and experience. An automatic tumor classification model is important to handle radiologists to detect the brain tumors. However, the precision of present model should be enhanced for appropriate treatments. Numerous computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) models are offered in the literary works of medical imaging to help radiologists concerning their patients. This paper proposes an optimization-driven technique, namely Whale Harris Hawks optimization (WHHO) for brain tumor detection using MR images. Here, segmentation is performed using cellular automata and rough set theory. In addition, the features are extracted from the segments, which include tumor size, Local Optical Oriented Pattern (LOOP), Mean, Variance, and Kurtosis. In addition, the brain tumor detection is carried out using deep convolutional neural network (DeepCNN), wherein the training is performed using proposed WHHO. The proposed WHHO is designed by integrating Whale optimization algorithm (WOA) and Harris hawks optimization (HHO) algorithm. The proposed WHHO-based DeepCNN outperformed other methods with maximal accuracy of 0.816, maximal specificity of 0.791, and maximal sensitivity of 0.974, respectively.

Ahmet Çinar et al. [9] Brain tumor is one of the dangerous and deadly cancer types seen in adults and children. Early and accurate diagnosis of brain tumor is important for the treatment

process. It is an important step for specialists to detect the brain tumor using computer aided systems. These systems allow specialists to perform tumor detection more easily. However, mistakes made with traditional methods are also prevented. In this paper, it is aimed to diagnose the brain tumor using MRI images. CNN models, one of the deep learning networks, are used for the diagnosis process. Resnet50 architecture, one of the CNN models, is used as the base. The last 5 layers of the Resnet50 model have been removed and added 8 new layers. With this model, 97.2% accuracy value is obtained. Also, results are obtained with Alexnet, Resnet50, Densenet201, InceptionV3 and Googlenet models. Of all these models, the model developed with the highest performance has classified the brain tumor images. As a result, when analyzed in other studies in the literature, it is concluded that the developed method is effective and can be used in computer-aided systems to detect brain tumor.

Muwei Jian et al. [10] In recent years, the issue of tumor detection for Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) brain images has become a research hotspot in the field of medical imaging, multimedia and pattern recognition. In this paper, we propose a tumor detection method based on saliency modeling for MRI brain images. Firstly, in order to overcome the influence of the skull, we utilize the morphological method to strip the skull of the MRI brain images. Then, we introduce a principal local contrast based saliency-detection method to enhance the foreground regions which facilitates to get the lesion region. Finally, the results are further improved by denoising, segmentation and morphological operations. Experiments performed on MRI brain images show that the proposed method is useful and effective.

Aditi Verma et al. [11] In medical imaging, the process of tumor detection is developing at a rapid rate. A tumor occurs when certain cells grow rapidly or uncontrollably. A brain tumor is also one of the rapidly developing diseases in the world; more than 120 different types of brain tumors occur and most of them are cancerous. Medical image processing is the most challenging and rapidly developing field. The detection of brain tumors from magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is also developing and has become a major topic of research. The main purpose of this study was to detect a tumor in the brain using three segmentation techniques, namely, k-means segmentation, image thresholding segmentation, and watershed segmentation. However, before the segmentation of the tumor, the MR image of the brain needs to be filtered. We used and compared four filtration techniques, namely, anisotropic filtering, adaptive filtering, median filtering, and unsharp mask filtering. The results show the implementation of all four filtration techniques. The results of all segmentation algorithms have also been discussed. After the completion of filtration and segmentation, we extracted certain optimal features of the tumor using the GLCM method. The table of extracted features with different datasets is also presented. These features provide

high-level information about the detected tumor. This study provides the necessary information about the tumor using four different kinds of filters; it also provides an understanding of how to obtain the correct filter. In addition, we used three different algorithms of segmentation to study their use and benefit.

Bhuvanjeet Singh Gandhi et al. [12] Brain tumor refers to a tissue group that is prearranged by abnormal cells being slowly incorporated. These cells uncontrollably multiply, apparently unaffected by the processes that regulate normal cells. The tumor of the brain can be broadly categorized into two categories: benign tumor and malignant tumor. As the presence of a tumor is harmful and may lead to the loss of life of the person, an accurate prediction of the tumor is a must. In this chapter, a novel technique that increases the detection accuracy of the brain tumor from magnetic resonance imaging images is presented. To increase the detection accuracy, the thresholded image is overlapped with the canny edge-detected output image. The resulted overlapped image is then inverted followed by watershed segmentation of the image. After this, the processed image is fed to the convolutional neural network model for predictions. In this way, the model's prediction accuracy has increased.

Alexander Zotin et al. [13] Nowadays, medical image processing is the most challenging and emerging field. Edge detection of MRI images is one of the most important stage in this field. The paper describes the proposed strategy to detect the edges of brain tumor from patient's MRI scan images of the brain. At the first stage, this method includes some noise removal functions improving features that provides better characteristics of medical images for reliable diagnosis using Balance Contrast Enhancement Technique (BCET). The result of second stage is subjected to image segmentation using Fuzzy c-Means (FCM) clustering method. Finally, Canny edge detection method is applied to detect the fine edges. During the experimental study, we used images containing brain tumors that were characterized by different location, type of pathology, shape, size and density, as well as the size of the area of the affected tissue near the tumor space. Detection and extraction of tumor from MRI scan images of the brain is done using MATLAB software. The obtained results demonstrate some resistivity to a noise. Also, the accuracy of segmentation, in some cases of tumor pathology, was increased up to 10-15% regarding the expert estimates.

K.S. Angel Viji et al. [14] In the analysis of brain Magnetic Resonance Images (MRI), classification of normality and abnormality is an important issue. Many works have been done to classify the brain MR images. This paper presents a new technique to classify the brain MRI images by using segmentation and KNN classifier. Initially, the brain MRI images obtained from brain databases are pre-processed using the Gaussian filter and the pre-processed images are

normalized. Subsequently, the normalized images are subjected to segmentation by employing texture and intensity oriented region growing technique (TIORGW). Then texture features are extracted from the segmented brain MRI images. Later that, the well-known optimization algorithm called Genetic Algorithm (GA) is utilized to select the optimal texture features. Following that, the optimal features are passed in to KNN in order to classify whether the brain MRI image is normal or not. The proposed technique is implemented in the working platform of MATLAB and the performance is analysed by utilizing more number of brain MRI images.

Solmaz Abbasi et al. [15] Brain tumor pathology is one of the most common mortality issues considered as an essential priority for health care societies. Accurate diagnosis of the type of disorder is crucial to make a plan for remedy that can minimize the deadly results. The main purpose of segmentation and detection is to make distinction between different regions of the brain. Besides accuracy, these techniques should be implemented quickly. In this paper an automatic method for brain tumor detection in 3D images has been proposed. In the first step, the bias field correction and histogram matching are used for pre-processing of the images. In the next step, the region of interest is identified and separated from the background of the Flair image. Local binary pattern in three orthogonal planes (LBP-TOP) and histogram of orientation gradients (HOG-TOP) are used as the learning features. Since 3D images are used in this research we use the idea of in local binary pattern in three orthogonal planes in order to extend histogram orientation gradients for 3D images. The random forest is then used to segment tumorous regions. We evaluate the performance of our algorithm on glioma images from BRATS 2013. Our experimental results and analyses indicate that our proposed framework is superior in detecting brain tumors in comparison with other techniques.

Table 1 Method

Method	Reference	Advantage	Limitation
Thresholding	[1-5]	Implementation is easy, and computation time is less.	1 Accuracy goes down in heterogeneous regions. 2 Not robust to noise. 3 Choosing threshold values is tricky.

Deep learning	[6-9]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Feature mapping can be adjusted based on the database. 2. Works in a complex environment as well. 3. Segmentation results are good compared to others. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 The network structure will be complex. 2 Computation time for training will be more. 3 System requirements are high.
Region-based	[10-15]	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Computation time is less. 2. Segmentation works well even in a complex environment. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Less performance during a noisy environment. 2. Requires post-processing and parameter initialization requires extensive analysis.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper reviews Brain tumor Detection techniques and algorithms. The process for the detection of brain tumors and types of segmentation and functions used by the algorithms are discussed. Along with it, we understand various models and their performance, and which performance metrics were used. This paper gives which techniques and metrics we can use for building a Brain tumor Detection System. In the review paper, fully automatic numerous segmentation methods are discussed to detect tumors in MRI images. At first, pre-processing is put into effect in which multiple input images are passed through various filters for the removal of noise. Once the pre-processing process is completed, the filtered image is segmented into the tumor, white matter (WM), grey matter (GM), and edema regions. Research is carried out on the extracted feature, and in conclusion, using various Machine learning approaches, these extracted features can be further classified as tumor and non-

tumor. Also, in the above table benefits and drawbacks of used segmentation methods are discussed, which will be convenient and fruitful for radiologists and medical students. Thus this review will act as a bridge to make advancements in the segmentation process for precise diagnosis.

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